

THERMOELECTRIC POWER OF SOME IN SITU COMPOSITES

A. S. Yue

Department of Materials Science and Engineering
School of Engineering and Applied Science
University of California
Los Angeles, California 90024, U. S . A.

ABSTRACT

The electrical resistivity, ρ , the thermal conductivity, k , the Seebeck coefficient, α , and the figure of merit, z , of directionally solidified platelet Mg-Mg₁₇Al₁₂ and Bi-Cd composites have been measured and calculated at room and liquid nitrogen temperatures. It was found that both α and z are anisotropic. The larger values are those measured in the direction parallel to the platelets and the smaller values are those measured in the direction perpendicular to them. The larger values of α and z for the Bi-Cd composite are interpreted in terms of Fermi energy level, effective electronic mass, electronic mobility, Debye temperature and lattice thermal characteristics.

1. INTRODUCTION

In situ composites for structural applications have been extensively investigated. However, very little has been known on their nonstructural applications. Since the publication of a series of review articles[1-4] on nonstructural applications of in situ composites, some work have been undertaken. In general, these applications are based on the combination of electrical, magnetic, optical and semiconducting properties such as magnetic resistors[5], infrared detectors[6], light sources[7], infrared polarizers[5,8,9], multijunction solar cells[10] and vacuum field emission cathode[11]. In this paper, we investigate the thermoelectric properties of Mg-Mg₁₇Al₁₂ and Bi-Cd in situ composites. The experimental results are presented with discussion.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Material and Sample preparation Growth of the Mg-Mg₁₇Al₁₂ composite (composite A) and the Bi-Cd composite (composite B) were carried out in a three-zone resistance-wound furnace, controlled with a 240 volt A.C. source through a magnetic amplifier. Mg, Al, Cd, and Bi shots of 99.999 and 99.9999 purity were weighed in right proportions and loaded in clean-fused-quartz tubes with closed conical ends. All the ampoules were vacuum-sealed at 10⁻⁶ Torr and homogenized at 500°C for two days in a rocking furnace. The homogenized ampoule was then placed inside a graphite crucible and covered with a graphite cap. The whole assembly was protected from oxidation by inserting it in a large size quartz container under vacuum. The growth process was taken place at a growth rate of 0.5cm per hr. and at a temperature gradient of 100°C per cm. The grown ingots were sliced with a string saw to rectangles (2 mm wide x 7 mm long with 1.7 mm in thickness) for electrical measurements.

2.2 Measurement of Thermoelectric properties The samples were mounted in a sample holder

essentially shown in Fig.1. The sample was soldered between heater and heatsink. Thermocouples and voltage probes were spark-welded to the sample by the capacitor-discharge method. The sample holder was then inserted in a stainless steel tube which was evacuated to a pressure of the order of 1mm. Thermal conductance from the sample holder to the liquid nitrogen bath was provided by immersing the bottom of the sample holder in a pool of gallium. This arrangement eliminated the need for a removal, low-temperature, vacuum seal.

Fig.1 Apparatus for Measurement of Thermoelectric and Thermomagnetic Effects

2.3 Measurement of Thermal Conductivity All thermal conductivity measurements at room temperature and below were made by an absolute method. A diagram of the test apparatus is shown in Fig. 2. The heater consists of a large number of turns of 0.005-in. constantan wire. This type of wire was chosen for its extremely low-temperature coefficient of resistivity ($2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{K}$ at room temperature). The resistance r of the heater was then measured on a precision Kelvin Bridge. The power input to the heater can therefore be accurately determined simply by the heater current i . The changes in the heater resistance with magnetic field were found to be negligible. The thermal conductivity apparatus shown in Fig. 2 has four gold-2.1 at% cobalt versus copper thermocouples. TC-1 is used to measure the ambient temperature while TC-2 is a differential thermocouple used to measure the temperature differential between the copper heatsink and copper holder. TC-2 typically indicates a temperature drop of less than 1°C across the silicone grease layer which acts as an electrical insulator. TC-3 and TC-4 are used to measure the temperature drop along the length of the sample. The reference junctions of TC-3 and TC-4 are attached to but electrically insulated from the heatsink by means of Duco cement.

Figure 2. Test Apparatus for Thermal Conductivity

3. RESULTS

Samples of directionally solidified composite A and composite B were examined with an optical microscope. SEM photographs revealed the platelet structure in the samples, similar to those reported elsewhere[10]. Rectangular specimens, 2mm wide x 7mm long with 1.7mm in thickness, were prepared for microstructural examination and for measurements of electrical resistivity, thermal conductivity, and thermoelectric power (Seebeck coefficient) in directions parallel and perpendicular to the platelets at room and liquid nitrogen temperatures. The experimental data obtained from these measurements are summarized in Table 1. From Table 1, it is seen that both ρ and k are not anisotropic for composite A and are anisotropic for composite B. The ratios of $\rho_{\parallel}/\rho_{\perp}$ of composite B at 80°K and 300°K are 2.9 and 4.4 and the ratio of k_{\parallel}/k_{\perp} is 1.5 at both temperatures. For composite A, the ratios of $\alpha_{\parallel}/\alpha_{\perp}$ at 80°K and 300°K are 3.5 and 1.9, respectively and the ratios of $\alpha_{\parallel}/\alpha_{\perp}$ for composite B are 7.3 and 4.7, respectively. The ratio of

$z_{||}/z_{\perp}$ is 3.5 at 300°K and it is 9.7 at 80°K. For composite B, the ratios are 5 and 8 for the corresponding temperatures. The differences in anisotropic effects for both composites are discussed in the following section.

Table 1. Seebeck Cefficients and Figures of Merits of Mg-Mg₁₇Al₁₂ and Bi-Cd In Situ Composites

Sample Number	Mg-Mg ₁₇ Al ₁₂				Bi-Cd				Unit
	Y-1		Y-2		Y-1		Y-2		
Measurement Temp.	80	300	80	300	80	300	80	300	°K
Figure of Merit, z	1.27 x10 ⁶	1.59 x10 ⁶	0.131 x 10 ⁶	0.455 x10 ⁶	0.69 x10 ⁻³	0.30 x10 ⁻³	0.09 x10 ⁻³	0.06 x10 ⁻³	per°K
Seebeck Ceffi., α*	-2.07	-3.00	-0.60	-1.6	-50.4	-49.7	-6.95	-10.7	μV/°C
Thermal Cond., k	0.28	0.28	0.28	0.28	0.142	0.142	0.092	0.092	w ^h Ccm
Resistivity, ρ	12.4	20.3	12.1	20.1	25.9	59.0	5.93	20.3	μΩcm

* Seebeck coefficient measured relative to copper.

4. DISCUSSION

The fundamental properties such as energy gap, Fermi energy level, carrier mobility, carrier concentration and thermal conductivity are essential to determine whether a material is suitable for thermoelectric power generation or not. Therefore, the following discussion on composites A and B is limited to resistivity, thermal conductivity, Seebeck coefficient, and figure of merit.

4.1 Resistivity By definition, the resistivity of a substance is expressed as $\rho = 1/ne\mu$ where n is the electron concentration, e is the electronic charge and μ is the electron mobility. When an electric current passes through a pair of conducting platelets of different resistivity in directions parallel and perpendicular to them, the total resistivity will exhibit an isotropic effect[4]. However, if the resistivity of both platelets are the same ($\rho_{\alpha} = \rho_{\beta}$), the total resistivity does not change regardless which direction the current is applied. Since the total resistivities of composite A measured at both directions are the same (12.4mw-cm at 80°K and 20.3mw-cm at 300°K), they do not exhibit an anisotropic effect. In the case of composite B, the ratio is 2.9 at 80°K and it is 4.4 at 300°K, indicating that the $\rho_{||}$ and ρ_{\perp} are not the same at any temperature.

4.2 Thermal Conductivity It is generally recognized that the total thermal conductivity, k_t , of a conductor is the sum of electronic, radiation, ambipolar and lattice thermal conductivities. The electronic contribution to k_t is due to the thermal energy transported by the conduction electrons and it is not the principal contribution to a thermoelectric material. The ambipolar contribution is due to diffusion of electron-hole pairs which does not play a role in metallic composites. In the same token, the radiation contribution for metal composites is negligible[12]. Therefore, the lattice thermal conductivity, k_l , is a major contribution to k_t . An expression derived by Leibfried and Shlomann[13] is

$$k_l = (\theta/\sigma)[MV^{1/3}/(\theta/T)] \cdot C \tag{1}$$

where θ = Debye temperature, M = atomic weight, V = atomic volume, T = absolute temperature and C = a constant, and

$$\sigma = \delta \ln \theta / \delta \ln V \quad (2)$$

and

$$\theta = A (T_m^3/M)^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

where T_m is the melting point of the thermoelectric material. From Eqns (1),(2), and (3), the higher the melting point of the thermoelectric material, the larger the value of the Debye temperature, θ , and the lattice thermal conductivity. Since the melting point of composite A is 437°C which is higher than the melting point of composite B material, 144°C, the lattice thermal conductivity of the former (0.28w/°C-cm) is greater than the latter (0.142w/°C-cm).

4.3 Seebeck Coefficient In the following discussion, we assume that both composite A and composite B behave like non-degenerate, extrinsic semiconductors to which Boltzmann statistics can apply. Consequently, the Seebeck coefficient is defined as

$$\alpha = (K/e)(\gamma - E_f/KT) \quad (4)$$

where K = Boltzmann constant, e = electric charge, E_f = Fermi energy, T = absolute temperature and γ (a material constant) = $s + 5/2$ where s is a scattering parameter, obtained from the energy dependence of the electron relaxation time and is equal to $-1/2$ due to acoustic mode of scattering for thermoelectric materials. The Fermi energy which is a measure of the extent of population of energy levels in the conduction band and is given by

$$E_f = KT [nh^3/2(2\pi m^*KT)^{3/2}] \quad (5)$$

where n = carrier concentration, h = Plank constant and m^* = carrier effective mass. Combination of the Eqns (4) and (5) yields

$$\alpha = - (K/e) \{ 2 + \ln[2(2\pi m^*KT)^{3/2}/nh^3] \} \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) essentially shows that α is inversely proportional to n . Since the electron concentrations of Bi(semimetal) and Cd are much less than those of Mg(metal) and Al(metal), the α of composite B is much larger than those of composite A as tabulated in Table 1. Also from Eqn (6) above, it can be seen that the higher the temperature T , the larger will be the α . This is the reason why $\alpha_{||}$ and α_{\perp} of both composites, measured at 300°K are larger than those measured at 80°K. The value of $\alpha_{||}$ is greater than that of α_{\perp} because the temperature gradient along the direction parallel to the platelet is smaller than that perpendicular to the platelet.

4.4 Figure of Merit By definition, the figure of merit is given by $z = \alpha^2/\rho k$ from which one can see that a good thermoelectric material should have a large Seebeck coefficient, a low electrical resistivity and a low thermal conductivity. It has been shown that doped semiconductors best fulfill these requirements. From Eqn (6) and the relationship $\rho = 1/ne\mu$, the Seebeck coefficient and electrical resistivity increase with increasing carrier concentration while the electronic contribution to the total thermal conductivity increases. By considering the contribution of n to maximize z , Heikes and Ure [14] concluded that

$$Z \propto m^{3/2}\mu/k_1 \quad (7)$$

where m^* is the effective mass of the carrier. Eqn (7) is an additional criterium for searching high z thermoelectric material. Furthermore, it is seen from Eqn (1) that the necessity for a small lattice thermal conductivity requires a choice of material with a low Debye temperature. In addition, an isotropic solid solution alloy yields a much smaller k_1 due to enhanced anharmonic forces between

the atoms in the lattice causing an increase in the number of phonon-phonon interactions. Although the Bi-Cd composite consists of parallel single-crystalline Bi and Cd platelets, they are not soluble in each other, forming a solid solution. As a result, its thermal conductivity value is 0.142 w/°C-cm as compared to a value of 0.02 w/°C-cm for the isotropic solid solution Bi-Sb alloy[15].

5. CONCLUSION

From the experimental data tabulated in Table 1 and the discussions on resistivity, thermal conductivity, Seebeck coefficient and figure of merit in the previous sections, the following conclusions can be drawn.

1. Thermoelectric figure of merit depends on the basic materials properties such as Fermi energy, carrier mobility, effective mass and lattice thermal conductivity.
2. Whether a material is potentially a good thermoelectric material or not depends on the quantity $m^{*3/2}\mu/k_1$.
3. To maintain a high figure of merit over a large temperature range, thermoelectric materials should possess a large amount of short-range disorder such as the isomorphous single-crystalline Bi-Sb alloys.
4. Thermoelectric materials with smaller molecular weight tend to have a lower figure of merit.
5. The figure of merit of the Bi-Cd composite (0.69×10^{-3} per °K) is not suitable for thermoelectric power application.

6. Acknowledgment

The author wishes to thank Drs. Steve and Milly Liu Foundation for the financial support and Mr. S.H. Choi for typing the manuscript.

7. REFERENCES

1. F. G. Galasso, F. C. Douglass, and J. A. Batt, Recent Studies of Eutectics for Nonstructural Applications, *J. of Metals*, **6**, 40 (1970).
2. M. B. Bever, P.E. Duwez, and W.A. Tiller, On Nonstructural Applications of Composites, *Master. Sci. Eng.*, **6**, 149 (1970).
3. W. Albers, Physical Properties of Composite Materials, *Proc. of the Conf. on In Situ Composites*, 1 September (1972).
4. A. S. Yue, A Review of In Situ Composites for Nonstructural Applications, *Conference on In Situ Composites III Ginn Custom Publishing, Lexington, Massachusetts*, 02173, 171 (1979).
5. H. Weiss, Electromagnetic Properties of Eutectic Composites (A Critical Review), *Met.Trans* **2**, 1513 (1971).
6. B. Paul and H. Weiss, Anisotropic Insb-NiSb as an Infrared Detector, *Solid State Electronics*, **11**, 979 (1968).
7. Br. Patent 1, 119, 215 (1968), Semiconductor Arrangements for Generating Electromagnetic Radiation in the range Consisting of the Infrared and Visible Spectral Ranges.
8. A. J. Sievers, Optical Properties of Composite Structures, *Proc. of the Conf. on In Situ Composites*, 129, September (1972).
9. A. S. Yue and J. G. Yu, Optical Properties of NaCl-NaF Eutectics, *Proc. of the Conference*

on *In Situ Composites* 11, 425 (1975).

10. A. S. Yue and J. G. Yu, Semiconducting Behavior of Eutectic Composites, *Proc. in Science and Engineering of Composites, ICCM-IV, Tokyo*, 1982.
11. Douglass A. Kirkpatrick, Paul E. Schoen, W.B. Stockton, R.Price, S. Baral, Brian E. Kahn, Joel M. Schnur, Mark Levinson, and Brian M. Ditchek, Measurements of Vacuum Field Emission From Bio - Molecular and Semiconductor - Metal Eutectic Composite Microstructures, *IEEE Trans. on Plasma Science*, 19, 5, October (1991).
12. J. A. Krumhansl and W. S. Williams, Thermal Conductivity in Solids, *Thermoelectricity* (edited by P.H.Egli), Willey, New york, 69 (1960).
13. G. Leibfried and E. Schlomann, Nachr, Akad. Wiss. Gottingen, *Math-Physik, Kl. Ila*, 4, 71 (1954).
14. R. R. Heikes and R. W. Ure, Jr., *Thermoelectricity : Science and Engineering*, Interscience Publishes, New York, 342 (1961).
15. A, S. Yue and L. R. Williams, Effect of Constitutional Supercooling on the Thermo-Magnetic Figure of Merit of Bi(95)Sb(5) Single Crystals. *Met. Trans. I*, 3462 (1970).

